

SUPPORTING INFORMATION: Efficient heating of single-molecule junctions for thermoelectric studies at cryogenic temperatures

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I. SI1. NULL-POINT METHOD: INDIVIDUAL APPROACH CURVES

FIG. S1: (a) - (c) Individual approach curves in which the probe at temperature T_{probe} is brought into contact with the (hot) drain lead at temperature T_{drain} for (a) $T_{\text{probe}} > T_{\text{drain}}$, (b) $T_{\text{probe}} = T_{\text{drain}}$ and (c) $T_{\text{probe}} < T_{\text{drain}}$. Increasing the tip position corresponds to a tip movement towards the sample.

II. SI2. NULL-POINT METHOD: CALIBRATION

FIG. S2: (a) - (d) Normalized SThM response jump (black open circles) for different power dissipated in the sample heater for probe excess temperatures ΔT_{probe} : (a) 11 K, (b) 13 K, (c) 19 K and (d) 31 K. The red solid line is the best linear fit of the measured points and the dashed lines depict the envelope of all possible linear fits. The blue solid circle is the zero-crossing point of the linear fit, where the (hot) drain contact and the probe tip apex have the same excess temperature ($\Delta T_{\text{apex}} = \Delta T_{\text{drain}}$). ΔT_{apex} is 88% of the calibrated

ΔT_{apex} as shown elsewhere¹. The normalized SThM response jump is given by $\Delta V/V = (V_{\text{oc}} - V_{\text{ic}})/V_{\text{oc}} = (T_{\text{oc}} - T_{\text{ic}})/T_{\text{oc}}$, where V_{oc} and V_{ic} are the SThM response when the probe is out-of-contact and in-contact with the sample, respectively. V_{oc} and V_{ic} are extracted from the approach curves (see Fig. S1). The drain-contact temperature is then given by: $T_{\text{drain}} = T_{\text{ic}} + \phi(T_{\text{ic}} - T_{\text{oc}})$ where T_{ic} and T_{oc} are the probe apex temperature when in-contact and out-of-contact with the drain lead and ϕ is a dimensionless constant.

III. SI3. AC THERMOVOLTAGE MEASUREMENT

FIG. S3: (a) False-color scanning electron micrograph of the single-molecule transistor architecture and schematic circuit diagram which indicates the terminals used for V_{th} measurements: an AC heater current $I_{\text{heater}}^f = 0.1$ mA (which corresponds to a temperature bias of 26 mK) at a frequency $f = 7$ Hz is applied to the sample heater. The drain contact is set to ground and the thermovoltage V_{th}^{2f} built up on the source contact is measured at a frequency $2f$. V_g is applied via the back gate with respect to ground. Scale bar: 2 μm .

IV. SI4. ESTIMATION OF ΔT FROM THE STHM DATA

The following methods are suggested to estimate the temperature drop ΔT on the single molecule:

1. Use the temperature gradient in Figure 2 (c) in the main text at the position of the molecular junction ($dT/dx = 1.3 \text{ K}/\mu\text{m}$) and the length of the molecule (about 1.5 nm). This yields a temperature drop of 2 mK and $d(\Delta T)/d(P_{\text{heater}}) = 5.1 \text{ K/W}$.
2. Use the temperatures of the left and right side of the gold bridge which yields $\Delta T = 1.4 \text{ K}$ and $d(\Delta T)/d(P_{\text{heater}}) = 3.7 \text{ K/mW}$.
3. Use the temperature difference between source and drain contact which yields $\Delta T = 3.5 \text{ K}$ and $d(\Delta T)/d(P_{\text{heater}}) = 9.5 \text{ K/mW}$.

We would like to stress that the magnitude of thermoelectric effects is given by the electron temperature. However, SThM and the resistance thermometry method are sensitive to the phonon temperature which can be substantially lower than the electron temperature. Due to this uncertainty we decided to use the largest ΔT value (the difference between source and drain contact temperatures) which yields an underestimation and lower bound for the thermoelectric parameters.

REFERENCES

¹P. Tovee, M. Pumarol, D. Zeze, K. Kjoller, and O. Kolosov, “Nanoscale spatial resolution probes for scanning thermal microscopy of solid state materials,” *Journal of Applied Physics* **112**, 114317 (2012).